

First results from the JUNO experiment

Davide Basilico on behalf of the JUNO collaboration

NuPhys 2026: Prospects in Neutrino Physics
2026 Jan 08 - King's College, London

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI MILANO

ν oscillations and Reactor experiments

Neutrino oscillations status

5 known:

Δm_{12}^2	$\sim 7 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ eV}^2$	(~2.3%)
$ \Delta m_{3l}^2 $	$\sim 2 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2$	(~0.8%)
$\sin^2 \theta_{12}$	~ 0.3	(~4.5%)
$\sin^2 \theta_{23}$	~ 0.5	(~4-5%)
$\sin^2 \theta_{13}$	~ 0.02	(~2.4%)

Capozzi, Lisi et al, Phys. Rev. D 111, 093006

Oscillations

s

Non-oscillations

several unknowns:

δ CPV Dirac phase

$\text{sign}(\Delta m_{3l}^2) \rightarrow$ neutrino mass ordering

θ_{23} octant degeneracy ($< 45^\circ$ or $> 45^\circ$)

physics beyond the 3 flavor paradigm?

absolute mass scale

Dirac/Majorana nature

Experiment	Dominant	Important
Solar Experiments	θ_{12}	$\Delta m_{21}^2, \theta_{13}$
Reactor LBL (KamLAND)	Δm_{21}^2	θ_{12}, θ_{13}
Reactor MBL (Daya-Bay, Reno, D-Chooz)	$\theta_{13}, \Delta m_{31,32}^2 $	
Atmospheric Experiments (SK, IC-DC)		$\theta_{23}, \Delta m_{31,32}^2 , \theta_{13}, \delta_{CP}$
Accel LBL $\nu_\mu, \bar{\nu}_\mu$, Disapp (K2K, MINOS, T2K, NO ν A)	$ \Delta m_{31,32}^2 , \theta_{23}$	
Accel LBL $\nu_e, \bar{\nu}_e$ App (MINOS, T2K, NO ν A)	δ_{CP}	θ_{13}, θ_{23}

S. Navas et al.
(Particle Data
Group), Phys. Rev. D
110, 030001 (2024)

Exploring different sectors, based on experimental design

Reactor experiments

- Nuclear reactors \rightarrow cascade of β decay of fission daughters \rightarrow pure, cost-effective, $\bar{\nu}_e$ source
- Extremely intense flux: $\sim 2 \cdot 10^{20} \bar{\nu}_e / \text{s} / \text{GW}_{\text{th}}$ \rightarrow a 1 GW core reactor emits more $\bar{\nu}_e$ in 1 min than current neutrino beams in 1 year

Jiangmen Underground Neutrino Observatory

Huge and multipurpose **liquid-scintillator** detector underground in Southern China.

Jiangmen Underground Neutrino Observatory

Huge and multipurpose **liquid-scintillator** detector underground in Southern China.
Main goal : determine the NMO and enter the precision era for neutrino oscillations via reactor $\bar{\nu}_e$ oscillations ($L = 52.5$ km baseline)

Why JUNO?

Precision spectroscopy of reactor $\bar{\nu}_e$ at medium baseline

First experiment to observe the interference of **fast** ($\sin^2\theta_{13}$, $|\Delta m^2_{3\ell}|$) and **slow** ($\sin^2\theta_{12}$, Δm^2_{21}) oscillations **in vacuum**

→ interference pattern depends on NMO

Why JUNO?

Precision spectroscopy of reactor $\bar{\nu}_e$ at medium baseline

First experiment to observe the interference of **fast** ($\sin^2\theta_{13}$, $|\Delta m^2_{3\ell}|$) and **slow** ($\sin^2\theta_{12}$, Δm^2_{21}) oscillations **in vacuum**

→ interference pattern depends on NMO

... no dependence on θ_{23} , δ_{CP} , small dependence on matter effects

→ **golden channel for NMO** & for precise measurements of $\sin^2\theta_{12}$, Δm^2_{21} , $|\Delta m^2_{3\ell}|$

Exemplary spectrum, 6y
(10^5 events, $\sigma_E/E = 3\%$ @ 1 MeV)

JUNO Collab, 2025 *Chinese Phys. C* 49 033104

JUNO detector

Detector design

Detector design

Liquid scintillator (20 kton)

- 20 kton of organic and ultrapure scintillator
- LAB (solvent) + 2.5 g/l PPO (fluor) + 3 mg/l Bis-MSB (shifter)
- $\sim 10^4$ photons emitted per MeV deposited energy
- Fluorescence emission peak ~ 430 nm, fast ~ 4.4 ns
- High transparency

LinearAlkylBenzene
(LAB) composition

Detector design

Inner Vessel

- Inner Diameter 35.4 m, thickness: 12 cm

assembly of two upper layers

Detector design

Stainless Steel Sphere

Detector design

Photomultiplier Tubes (PMTs)

- 17612 20-inch (large) PMTs, 25612 3-inch (small) PMTs
- Geometric coverage $\sim 78\%$
- QE $\sim 25\text{-}30\%$
- dark count rate $\sim 20\text{-}25$ kHz

20 inch PMTs (Large)

3 inch PMTs (Small)

Detector design

Top tracker

- **Muon veto**, refurbished OPERA (LNGS) scintillators
- 3 layers, ~60% coverage on the top

Water Pool cylinder (PMT-instrumented)

- 35 kton of high pure water as **shield**
- 2400 PMTs for active **muon veto**
detection efficiency > 99.9%

JUNO commissioning & performances

Timeline

2015

2022

Dec. 1, 2024

Civil construction

Detector construction

End of detector installation!

- SS structure built from bottom to top, then, acrylic built from the top to bottom
- Acrylic: high transparency (>96%) and low surface background (<5 ppt U/Th in 50 um thickness)

Timeline

Dec. 2024

Feb 1, 2025

Feb 8, 2025

Aug 26, 2025

Water Filling
Liquid Scintillator filling
Physics Data-Taking

2024 Dec: Water filling start

LS filling: June snapshot

2-steps filling process:

- 1) fill with water first
- 2) gradually replace water by LS inside acrylic sphere, from the top to the bottom: LS less dense than water and not chemically mixable

Key challenges

1) Large statistics

→ huge scintillator mass, powerful nuclear reactors

Key challenges

1) Large statistics

→ huge scintillator mass, powerful nuclear reactors

2) Cleanliness & low background (^{238}U , ^{232}Th)

→ LS purification + material cleaning and screening + tight radiopurity controls

$< 1 \cdot 10^{-16}$ g/g for ^{238}U and ^{232}Th chains

Key challenges

1) Large statistics

→ huge scintillator mass, powerful nuclear reactors

2) Cleanliness & low background (^{238}U , ^{232}Th)

→ LS purification + material cleaning and screening + tight radiopurity controls

$< 1 \cdot 10^{-16}$ g/g for ^{238}U and ^{232}Th chains

3) Stable detector operations

→ low-level PMT characterization & calibrations, commissioning tests

Key challenges

1) Large statistics

→ huge scintillator mass, powerful nuclear reactors

2) Cleanliness & low background (^{238}U , ^{232}Th)

→ LS purification + material cleaning and screening + tight radiopurity controls

$< 1 \cdot 10^{-16}$ g/g for ^{238}U and ^{232}Th chains

3) Stable detector operations

→ low-level PMT characterization & calibrations, commissioning tests

4) Well-known detector response

energy resolution goal
3.1% @1 MeV + 1%
control of the energy scale

→ LS optical properties + light collection + detector calibrations

Key challenges

1) Large statistics

→ huge scintillator mass, powerful nuclear reactors

2) Cleanliness & low background (^{238}U , ^{232}Th)

→ LS purification + material cleaning and screening + tight radiopurity controls

$< 1 \cdot 10^{-16}$ g/g for ^{238}U and ^{232}Th chains

3) Stable detector operations

→ low-level PMT characterization & calibrations, commissioning tests

4) Well-known detector response

energy resolution goal
3.1% @1 MeV + 1%
control of the energy scale

→ LS optical properties + light collection + detector calibrations

Detector calibrations

Artificial sources deployed in multiple positions: 1D and 2D systems
 γ and ^{241}Am - ^{13}C (neutrons) sources along the vertical axis

Energy response

Energy nonlinearity @ CD center, γ calib.

- constrained via γ , n calibrations and cosmogenic ^{12}B , ^{11}C events
- **nonlinearity assessed at better than 1% level**

Energy resolution @ CD center, γ calib.

- Energy resolution: **3.4%** @ 1.022 MeV (^{68}Ge)
- Light yield: ~ 1600 p.e./MeV for ^{68}Ge , better than design requirements

First measurement of reactor
oscillations at JUNO [arXiv:2511.14593](https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.14593)

$\bar{\nu}_e$ candidates selection

- Dataset: 59.1 days (August 30th - November 2nd)
- Selection strategy:
 - μ and μ -followers veto
 - time-space coincidence
 - energy selection
- IBD reaction $\bar{\nu}_e + p \rightarrow e^+ + n$: time and spatial coincidence of prompt and delayed events
→ 47.9 ± 2.6 counts per day

Data selection & backgrounds

Irreducible backgrounds : mimicking the IBD signature, 14% of the total events budget

- cosmogenic isotopes (${}^9\text{Li}$ - ${}^8\text{He}$) decaying β^- and n
- geoneutrinos: $\bar{\nu}_e$ from the Earth
- $\bar{\nu}_e$ from other far reactors

Antineutrinos ($\bar{\nu}_e$) Candidates Summary		
DAQ live time (days)	59.1	
$\bar{\nu}_e$ candidates	2379	
$\bar{\nu}_e$ signal (cpd¹)		
w/o ε_{tot} corrected	33.5 ± 1.7	
w/ ε_{tot} corrected	47.9 ± 2.6	
Non-oscillated $\bar{\nu}_e$	150.9 ± 2.7	
Backgrounds (cpd)		
${}^9\text{Li}/{}^8\text{He}$	Pre-fit	Best-fit
	4.3 ± 1.4	3.9 ± 0.6
Geoneutrinos	1.2 ± 0.5	1.4 ± 0.4
World reactors	0.88 ± 0.09	0.88 ± 0.09
${}^{214}\text{Bi}$ - ${}^{214}\text{Po}$	0.18 ± 0.10	0.20 ± 0.10
${}^{13}\text{C}(\alpha, n){}^{16}\text{O}$	0.04 ± 0.02	0.04 ± 0.02
Fast neutrons	0.02 ± 0.02	0.02 ± 0.02
Double neutrons	0.05 ± 0.05	0.07 ± 0.05
Atmospheric neutrinos	0.08 ± 0.04	0.07 ± 0.04
Accidentals ($\times 10^{-2}$)	4.9 ± 0.3	4.9 ± 0.3

sig

bkg

The first JUNO reactor $\bar{\nu}_e$ spectrum

- Three internal independent analysis, fully consistent results
- Visible Δm^2_{21} -driven pattern \rightarrow large amount of missing events (rate) & slow oscillation (shape)
- Fast Δm^2_{31} -driven oscillations not assessed due to low statistics
- Non-oscillated $\bar{\nu}_e$ reference spectrum taken by Daya-Bay results

Best-fit values:

$$\sin^2\theta_{12} = 0.3092 \pm 0.0087 \text{ (2.81\%)}$$
$$\Delta m^2_{21} = (7.50 \pm 0.12) \times 10^{-5} \text{ eV}^2 \text{ (1.55\%)}$$

$\sin^2\theta_{12}$ and Δm^2_{12} : global picture

1.6× precision wrt PDG 2025 → world leading precision!

What next?

Oscillation physics perspectives

Sensitivity to mixing angles & Δm^2

$\sin^2\theta_{12}, \Delta m_{21}^2, |\Delta m_{31}^2|$: **6 years**: precision $< 0.5\%$
 (~1 oom improvement wrt PDG 2025)

Sensitivity to Neutrino Mass Ordering

3σ measurement expected
 with JUNO-data only in ~7 years!

Oscillation physics perspectives

Sensitivity to mixing angles & Δm^2

$\sin^2\theta_{12}, \Delta m_{21}^2, |\Delta m_{31}^2|$: **6 years**: precision $< 0.5\%$
 (~1 oom improvement wrt PDG 2025)

Sensitivity to Neutrino Mass Ordering

3σ measurement expected
 with JUNO-data only in ~7 years!

& lots of other non-reactor goals (geo- ν , solar ν , atmospheric ν)...

STAY TUNED

Conclusion

JUNO is a multipurpose neutrino detector, commissioning & filling completed in August 2025;
→ stable detector performance, globally meeting design expectations

Oscillation results released by analyzing the first 59 days of data taking

→ 1.6× precision improvement wrt PDG 2025 for $\sin^2\theta_{12}$ and Δm_{21}^2

A lot of work ongoing:

- Deep detector characterization, understanding and calibrations ongoing
- Looking forward Δm_{31}^2 / NMO measurements & natural ν sources results!

Thanks!

Backup

Position reconstruction

3 different vertex reconstructions tested using 68 Ge calibration
Biases within 10 cm is most of detector
Resolution typically from 15 cm to 20 cm depending on algorithm

IBD candidate selection

- FV cut: prompt candidate vertices with $R < 16.5$ m and $|z| < 15.5$ m
 - ▶ Slight differences between analysis I, II, and III
 - ▶ Each analysis used different vertex reconstruction algorithm
- Flasher rejection based on std-dev of PMT hit multiplicity & timing distributions
- μ veto
 - ▶ μ : CD triggers with $Q > 3 \cdot 10^4$ PE or WP triggers with $Q > 700$ PE
 - ★ Reject events within 5 ms following a μ
 - ★ One analysis also tested cylindrical cut around μ but not chosen as baseline for now
 - ▶ Spallation neutron: $\Delta t_{\mu} \in [40 \mu\text{s}, 2 \text{ ms}]$ and $E \in [1.5, 20] \text{ MeV}$
 - ★ Reject events within 4 m of a spallation neutron up to 1.2 s after the neutron
- Multiplicity: reject events with extra energy deposits close to delayed signal
- Prompt-delayed coincidence (ie, IBD-like)
 - ▶ Prompt energy: $E_p \in [0.7, 12.0] \text{ MeV}$
 - ▶ Delayed energy: $E_d \in [2.0, 2.5] \text{ MeV}$
 - ▶ Time interval: $\Delta t \in [5 \mu\text{s}, 1 \text{ ms}]$
 - ▶ Spatial separation: $\Delta d < 1.5 \text{ m}$

PMT system

All PMTs produced, tested, and instrumented with waterproof potting

		LPMT (20-inch)		SPMT (3-inch)
		Hamamatsu	NNVT	HZC
Quantity		5000	15012	25600
Charge Collection		Dynode	MCP	Dynode
Photon Detection Efficiency		28.5%	30.1%	25%
Mean Dark Count Rate [kHz]	Bare	15.3	49.3	0.5
	Potted	17.0	31.2	
Transit Time Spread (σ) [ns]		1.3	7.0	1.6
Dynamic range for [0-10] MeV		[0, 100] PEs		[0, 2] PEs
Coverage		75%		3%
Reference		arXiv: 2205.08629		NIM.A 1005 (2021) 165347

12.6k NNVT PMTs with highest PDE are selected for light collection from LS and the rest are used in the Water Cherenkov detector.

An IBD event in JUNO

Prompt e^+ signal

Mon, 25 Aug 2025 22:50:45
RecEnergy = 6.3 MeV
RecVertex (-9458, -9707, 3820) mm

Delayed n signal

Mon, 25 Aug 2025 22:50:45
RecEnergy = 2.4 MeV
RecVertex (-10393, -9794, 4333) mm

Muon detection

JUNO cleanliness

- Radiopurity control of raw materials (JHEP 11 (2021) 102)
 - ▶ Careful screening of materials
 - ▶ 15% better than specifications!
- Radiopurity control during installation/filling
 - ▶ Leak check of all joints for ^{222}Rn and ^{85}Kr
 - ▶ Cleaning/washing of all pipes & vessels
 - ▶ Clean room environment during installation
 - ▶ Acrylic surface treatment & protection
 - ▶ LS filling after water washing & replacing water

Veto Water

- U/Th < $0.4 \cdot 10^{-15}$ g/g
- ^{222}Rn < 10 mBq/m³
- ^{226}Rn < 1 mBq/m³
- Single (R < 17.2 m & E > 0.7 MeV) rates < 7 Hz (design 7.2 Hz)

* Borexino: PRL 101 (2008) 091302

LS: very close to other solar ν exp

	JUNO	Borexino*
^{238}U	< $3 \cdot 10^{-17}$ g/g (small FV) < $1 \cdot 10^{-16}$ g/g (from Rn fit)	$(1.6 \pm 0.1)10^{-17}$ g/g
^{232}Th	< $1 \cdot 10^{-16}$ g/g (R<13 m)	$(6.8 \pm 1.5)10^{-18}$ g/g
^{210}Po	< $1 \cdot 10^5$ cpd/kt	$8 \cdot 10^4$ cpd/kt

- Likely impossible to recirculate LS

Non uniformity of energy resolution

Light yield

- Light yield from n-H capture in center of detector:

- ▶ Our last expectation (Chin.Phys.C 49 (2025) 1, 013003): 1665 PE/MeV
 - ★ This was used for our last NMO paper
- ▶ Measurement using JUNO data: 1785 PE/MeV
 - ★ About 10% larger than expected!

Residual nonlinearity

3ν status

Why this is so important?

- 1) Enter the **precision era** :
<1% determination of θ , Δm^2
- 2) NMO determination helps other experiments:
 - to determine any **leptonic CP** violation (δ_{CP}): remove NMO- δ_{CP} degeneracies
 - driving **next-gen 0 $\nu\beta\beta$ experiments**
strategy: do they have any hope of determining Dirac/Majorana nature?
- 3) highlight possible **tensions with Λ CDM model**? DESI + CMB results

several unknowns:

δ CPV Dirac phase

$\text{sign}(\Delta m_{3\ell}^2) \rightarrow$ neutrino mass ordering

θ_{23} octant degeneracy (< 45° or > 45°?)

physics beyond the 3 flavor paradigm?

absolute mass scale

Dirac/Majorana nature

Neutrino Mass Ordering (NMO)

absolute mass scale

Two mass splittings:

$$\Delta m_{21}^2 \sim 7 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ eV}^2 \quad \left| \Delta m_{3\ell}^2 \right| \sim 3 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2$$

small mass splitting large mass splitting

Normal Ordering $\longrightarrow \Delta m_{3\ell}^2 = \Delta m_{31}^2 > 0$

Inverted Ordering $\longrightarrow \Delta m_{3\ell}^2 = \Delta m_{32}^2 < 0$

Neutrino Mass Ordering (NMO)

Why is it so important?

- 1) **Missing tile** for the fundamental comprehension of neutrinos
- 2) Enter the **precision era** : < 1% determination of θ_{23} , Δm^2 splittings
- 3) Help other experiments to determine any **leptonic CP** violation (δ_{CP}): remove NMO- δ_{CP} degeneracies
- 4) Driving the strategy for the **next-gen 0 $\nu\beta\beta$ experiments** : can they determine the Dirac/Majorana nature?
- 5) With absolute ν mass experiments: highlight possible **tensions with cosmology models** ?

Normal Ordering $\longrightarrow \Delta m_{3\ell}^2 = \Delta m_{31}^2 > 0$

Inverted Ordering $\longrightarrow \Delta m_{3\ell}^2 = \Delta m_{32}^2 < 0$

- 1) Matter oscillations for atm. and acc. ν
- 2) Δm^2 's interference in vacuum osc.

JUNO collaboration

Country	Institute	Country	Institute	Country	Institute
Armenia	Yerevan Physics Institute	China	U. of South China	Italy	INFN Catania
Belgium	Universite Libre de Bruxelles	China	Wu Yi U.	Italy	INFN di Frascati
Brazil	PUC	China	Wuhan U.	Italy	INFN-Ferrara
Brazil	UEL	China	Xi'an JT U.	Italy	INFN-Milano
Chile	SAPHIR	China	Xiamen University	Italy	INFN-Milano Bicocca
Chile	UNAB	China	Zhengzhou U.	Italy	INFN-Padova
China	BISEE	China	NUDT	Italy	INFN-Perugia
China	CAGS	China	CUG-Beijing	Italy	INFN-Roma 3
China	ChongQing University	China	ECUT-Nanchang City	Pakistan	PINSTECH (PAEC)
China	DGUT	China	CDUT-Chengdu	Russia	INR Moscow
China	Guangxi U.	Czech	Charles U.	Russia	JINR
China	Harbin Institute of Technology	Finland	University of Jyvaskyla	Russia	MSU
China	IHEP	France	IJCLab Orsay	Slovakia	FMPICU
China	Jinan U.	France	LP2i Bordeaux	Taiwan-China	National Chiao-Tung U.
China	Nanjing U.	France	CPPM Marseille	Taiwan-China	National Taiwan U.
China	Nankai U.	France	IPHC Strasbourg	Taiwan-China	National United U.
China	NCEPU	France	Subatech Nantes	Thailand	NARIT
China	Shandong U.	Germany	RWTH Aachen U.	Thailand	PPRLCU
China	Shanghai JT U.	Germany	TUM	Thailand	SUT
China	IGG-Beijing	Germany	U. Hamburg	U.K.	U. Liverpool
China	SYSU	Germany	GSI	U.K.	U. Warwick
China	Tsinghua U.	Germany	U. Mainz	USA	UMD-G
China	UCAS	Germany	U. Tuebingen	USA	UC Irvine

Timeline

2015

2022

Dec. 2024

Feb. 2025

Civil construction

excavations underground

Water Pool inside (and empty)

Timeline

2015

2022

Dec. 2024

Feb. 2025

Civil construction

Detector construction

Key challenges for JUNO

1) Large statistics

→ huge scintillator mass, powerful nuclear reactors

2) Energy resolution: 3% @ 1 MeV + 1% control of the energy scale

→ LS optical properties + light collection + calibrations

energy non-uniformity
(~0.8%) → calibrations

$$\frac{\sigma_E}{E} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{a}{\sqrt{E}}\right)^2 + b^2 + \left(\frac{c}{E}\right)^2}$$

noise, Cherenkov (~1%)

Poisson statistical fluctuations (~2.6%)

→ the more light, the better!

Optimization of energy resolution

$$\frac{\sigma_{E_{\text{vis}}^{\text{prompt}}}}{E_{\text{vis}}^{\text{prompt}}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{a}{\sqrt{E_{\text{vis}}^{\text{prompt}}}}\right)^2 + b^2 + \left(\frac{c}{E_{\text{vis}}^{\text{prompt}}}\right)^2}$$

Effective parametrization for energy resolution
 → each terms cover multiple effects, but mainly:

- “a” term → Poisson statistical fluctuations (~2.6%)
- “b” term → energy non-uniformity (~0.8%)
- “c” term → background noise term (~1%)

enabling non-ideal effects

Assumptions	a	b	c	$\bar{a} = \sqrt{a^2 + (1.6b)^2 + (\frac{c}{1.6})^2}$
Central IBDs	2.62(2)	0.73(1)	1.38(4)	2.99(1)
Ideal correction	2.57(2)	0.73(1)	1.25(4)	2.93(1)
Azimuthal symmetry	2.57(2)	0.78(1)	1.26(4)	2.96(1)
Single gamma source	2.57(2)	0.80(1)	1.24(4)	2.98(1)
Finite calibration points	2.57(2)	0.81(1)	1.23(4)	2.98(1)
Vertex smearing(8 cm/ $\sqrt{E(\text{MeV})}$)	2.60(2)	0.82(1)	1.27(4)	3.01(1)
PMT QE random variations	2.61(2)	0.82(1)	1.23(4)	3.02(1)

Non-uniformity is corrected by calibrations with radioactive sources located in multiple positions

→ radial-angular function to correct reconstructed energy

(“optimizing energy resolution”)

Key challenges for JUNO

1) Large statistics

→ huge scintillator mass, powerful nuclear reactors

2) Energy resolution: 3% @ 1 MeV + 1% control of the energy scale

→ LS optical properties + light collection + calibrations

3) Low background

→ underground + scintillator purification system + material screening + veto systems

Bkg scenario	^{238}U and ^{232}Th [g/g]	Reference
High	10^{-15}	minimum NMO requirement
Medium	10^{-16}	100x worse wrt Borexino Phase-I
Low	10^{-17}	10x worse wrt Borexino Phase-I
Very Low	$\sim 10^{-19}$ (^{238}U) $\sim 5 \cdot 10^{-19}$ (^{232}Th)	Borexino Phase-III

Key challenges for JUNO

1) Large statistics

→ huge scintillator mass, powerful nuclear reactors

2) Energy resolution: 2.95% @ 1MeV + 1% understanding of the intrinsically non-linear energy scale

→ LS optical properties + light collection + calibrations

3) Low background

→ underground + scintillator purification system + material screening + veto systems

distillation plant

Top Tracker

Water Pool

Key challenges for JUNO

1) Large statistics

→ huge scintillator mass, powerful nuclear reactors

2) Energy resolution: 3% @ 1 MeV + 1% control of the energy scale

→ LS optical properties + light collection + calibrations

3) Low background

→ underground + scintillator purification system + material screening
+ veto systems

4) Knowledge of reactor spectra at sub-% level

→ near detector: Taishan Antineutrino Observatory (TAO), 44 m from
Taishan reactor

TAO detector during the assembly

[arXiv:2005.08745](https://arxiv.org/abs/2005.08745)

Liquid scintillator purification chain

5000 m³ LAB storage tank

1) Al₂O₃ for optical transparency

2) Distillation for radiopurity

2.4%

Mixing LAB with PPO and bis-MSB

97.6%

Mixing

85%

Commissioning

Monitoring pre-detector (OSIRIS)

15%

4) Gas stripping to remove Rn and O₂

3) Water extraction to remove radioactive impurities

1800 m SS pipes to underground

Reactor experiments

Wide L/E range to explore different oscillation features

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e) = & 1 - \cos^4(\theta_{13}) \sin^2(2\theta_{12}) \sin^2(\Delta_{21}) \\
 & - \cos^2(\theta_{12}) \sin^2(2\theta_{13}) \sin^2(\Delta_{31}) \\
 & - \sin^2(\theta_{12}) \sin^2(2\theta_{13}) \sin^2(\Delta_{32})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Delta_{kj} = 1.27 \Delta m_{kj}^2 [\text{eV}^2] \frac{L[\text{m}]}{E[\text{MeV}]}$$

Reactor experiments

Wide L/E range to explore different oscillation features

Medium baseline ($\theta_{12}, \Delta m_{21}^2$)

$$P(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e) = 1 - \cos^4(\theta_{13}) \sin^2(2\theta_{12}) \sin^2(\Delta_{21})$$

$$- \cos^2(\theta_{12}) \sin^2(2\theta_{13}) \sin^2(\Delta_{31})$$

Short baseline ($\theta_{13}, \Delta m_{31}^2$)

$$\Delta_{kj} = 1.27 \Delta m_{kj}^2 [\text{eV}^2] \frac{L[\text{m}]}{E[\text{MeV}]}$$

Why JUNO?

$$P(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e) = 1 - \cos^4(\theta_{13}) \sin^2(2\theta_{12}) \sin^2(\Delta_{21}) - \cos^2(\theta_{12}) \sin^2(2\theta_{13}) \sin^2(\Delta_{31}) - \sin^2(\theta_{12}) \sin^2(2\theta_{13}) \sin^2(\Delta_{32})$$

NMO drives the sign and the absolute value of $|\Delta m_{3l}^2| \rightarrow$ differences in oscillation L/E profiles!

Maximum relative NO/IO difference:
 optimized baseline $L = 52.5$ km
 [JHEP 01 (2019) 106]

JUNO

Why JUNO?

NMO drives the sign and the absolute value of $|\Delta m_{3\ell}^2|$
→ oscillation probability profiles vs L/E are **phased out** !

$$P(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e) = 1 - \cos^4(\theta_{13}) \sin^2(2\theta_{12}) \sin^2(\Delta_{21}) \\ - \cos^2(\theta_{12}) \sin^2(2\theta_{13}) \sin^2(\Delta_{31}) \\ - \sin^2(\theta_{12}) \sin^2(2\theta_{13}) \sin^2(\Delta_{32})$$

$$\Delta_{kj} = 1.27 \Delta m_{kj}^2 [\text{eV}^2] \frac{L[\text{m}]}{E[\text{MeV}]}$$

Why JUNO?

NMO drives the sign and the absolute value of $|\Delta m_{3l}^2|$

→ Maximum relative NO/IO difference: **optimized baseline L = 52.5 km**

Neutrino oscillations in a nutshell

Quantum superposition of ν mass eigenstates leads to ν oscillation

$$\begin{pmatrix} \nu_e \\ \nu_\mu \\ \nu_\tau \end{pmatrix} = U_{\text{PMNS}} \begin{pmatrix} \nu_1 \\ \nu_2 \\ \nu_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$U_{\text{PMNS}} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_{23} & s_{23} \\ 0 & -s_{23} & c_{23} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{13} & 0 & s_{13}e^{-i\delta_{\text{CP}}} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s_{13}e^{i\delta_{\text{CP}}} & 0 & c_{13} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{12} & s_{12} & 0 \\ -s_{12} & c_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

mixing angles

$$c_{ij} = \cos \theta_{ij}$$

$$s_{ij} = \sin \theta_{ij}$$

$$P(\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta) \sim \sin^2(2\theta) \sin\left(\frac{L}{4E} \Delta m^2\right)$$

L: source-detector distance

E: neutrino energy

Δm^2 : squared mass splitting

amplitude

frequency

Neutrino oscillations

Atmospheric ν

$L \sim 10^3 - 10^4$ km,
 $E \sim 10^2 - 10^4$ MeV
+ matter effects

- SuperKamioKaNDE: 1988 →
- IceCube 2010 →
- KM3NeT: 2022 →
- **JUNO: 2025** →

+

Accelerator ν

$L \sim 10^2 - 10^3$ km
 $E \sim 10^3$ MeV
+ matter effects

- T2K: 2010 →
- NOvA: 2014 →
- HyperK: 2027?
- DUNE: 2030?

+

Reactor ν

$L \sim 1 - 10^2$ km
 $E \sim$ MeV

- KamLAND: 2002 →
- RENO: 2011 →
- **JUNO: 2025** →
- + short-baseline reactors

Several experiments at a maturity stage, others set to begin or be upgraded

Sensitivity to NMO

Mass ordering sum rule for the neutrino disappearance channels in T2K, NOvA, and JUNO,
Parke, Denton, Phys.Rev.D 110 (2024) 7, 073005

Synergy: JUNO+T2K+NOvA

Combine the $\sim 1.2\%$ Δm_{31}^2 from T2K+NOvA with the JUNO expected one Δm_{31}^2 in 1 year ($\sim 0.8\%$). Do they align?

$>3\sigma$ determination of the NMO could be achieved in ~ 1 year of JUNO data taking, ONLY IF JUNO aligns with Normal Ordering (NO), which is preferred by pre-JUNO experiments in the current global analysis

Sensitivity to MeV solar ν

Goals: solar metallicity puzzle (mainly based on CNO ν) + oscillations + Non-Standard Interactions

Expected energy spectrum, 6y, Medium bkg scenario (10^{-16} g/g for ^{238}U and ^{232}Th)

spectral analysis

JCAP 10 (2023) 022

For most of the background scenarios JUNO will improve the best results on solar ν fluxes (Borexino).

Global 3ν oscillation analysis: best-fit values and 1σ ranges

Parameter	Ordering	Best fit	1σ range	" 1σ " (%)
$\delta m^2 / 10^{-5} \text{ eV}^2$	NO, IO	7.37	7.21 – 7.52	2.3
$\sin^2 \theta_{12} / 10^{-1}$	NO, IO	3.03	2.91 – 3.17	4.5
$ \Delta m^2 / 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2$	NO	2.495	2.475 – 2.515	0.8
	IO	2.465	2.444 – 2.485	0.8
$\sin^2 \theta_{13} / 10^{-2}$	NO	2.23	2.17 – 2.27	2.4
	IO	2.23	2.19 – 2.30	2.4
$\sin^2 \theta_{23} / 10^{-1}$	NO	4.73	4.60 – 4.96	5.1
	IO	5.45	5.28 – 5.60	4.3
δ / π	NO	1.20	1.07 – 1.37	18
	IO	1.48	1.36 – 1.61	8
$\Delta\chi_{\text{IO-NO}}^2$	IO-NO	+5.0		

Small ("solar")
mass splitting

$$\delta m^2 = m_2^2 - m_1^2 > 0$$

Large ("atmospheric")
mass splitting

$$\Delta m^2 = m_3^2 - \frac{1}{2}(m_1^2 + m_2^2)$$

II. HOW CAN ν_e DISAPPEARANCE MEASUREMENT ALONE SIGNAL THE NEUTRINO MASS HIERARCHY?

The vacuum ν_e survival probability using $\Delta_{ij} \equiv \Delta m_{ij}^2 L/4E$ ($\Delta m_{ij}^2 \equiv m_i^2 - m_j^2$) as shorthand for the kinematical phase, can be written without any approximation as

$$\begin{aligned} P(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e) &= 1 - 4|U_{e3}|^2|U_{e1}|^2 \sin^2 \Delta_{31} - 4|U_{e3}|^2|U_{e2}|^2 \sin^2 \Delta_{32} - P_{\odot}, \\ &= 1 - \frac{1}{2} \sin^2 2\theta_{13} [1 - (c_{12}^2 \cos 2\Delta_{31} + s_{12}^2 \cos 2\Delta_{32})] - P_{\odot}, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where the usual parameterization of the mixing matrix [19] is used with the abbreviations $c_{ij} \equiv \cos \theta_{ij}$ and $s_{ij} \equiv \sin \theta_{ij}$. Here E is the neutrino energy and L is the baseline distance. P_{\odot} , as defined by,

$$P_{\odot} \equiv 4|U_{e2}|^2|U_{e1}|^2 \sin^2 \Delta_{21} = \sin^2 2\theta_{12} c_{13}^4 \sin^2 \Delta_{21}, \quad (2)$$

is the oscillation probability associated with the solar Δm^2 scale. In this paper, we assume the standard three neutrino framework with CPT conservation (except for where we discuss possible CPT violation), which implies that Eq. (1) is also valid for $\bar{\nu}_e$.

The neutrino mass hierarchy can be determined if one knows which kinematical phase, $|\Delta_{31}|$ or $|\Delta_{32}|$, is larger. Namely, if $|\Delta_{31}| > |\Delta_{32}|$ the normal hierarchy is the case, and if $|\Delta_{31}| < |\Delta_{32}|$ the inverted one. How we can know which is larger? When two waves with slight different frequencies travel together there arises the phenomenon of beating. The

Sterile neutrinos: fading away?

Unlike a few years ago, sterile ν no longer able to simultaneously explaining anomalies sharing the same channel.

New experimental data required, as upgraded VSBL reactor experiments (KATRIN, PROSPECT-II, JUNO-TAO, DANSS)

If $\nu e \rightarrow \nu e$ and $\nu\mu \rightarrow \nu e$ anomalies confirmed, new physics needed: extra sterile states + something else (intense theoretical effort)

Explanations beyond the Standard Model

ν_s coupled to ultralight DM (MSW resonance, Sec. 5.1.1)	several exotic ingredients; somewhat tuned MSW resonance; new ν_4 decay channel required for cosmology.	★★★★☆
ν_s coupled to dark energy (MSW resonance, Sec. 5.1.2)	several exotic ingredients; somewhat tuned MSW resonance; cosmology similar to the previous scenario.	★★★☆☆
ν_s coupled to ultralight DM (param. resonance, Sec. 5.1.3)	several exotic ingredients; somewhat tuned parametric resonance; cosmology requires post-BBN DM production via misalignment.	★★★★☆
decaying ν_s (Section 5.2)	difficult to reconcile with reactor and solar data; regeneration of active neutrinos in ν_s decays alleviates tension, but does not resolve it.	★★☆☆☆
vanilla eV-scale ν_s (Refs. [17, 18])	preferred parameter space is strongly disfavored by solar and reactor data.	★☆☆☆☆
ν_s with CPT violation (Refs. [130])	avoids constraints from reactor experiments, but those from solar neutrinos cannot be alleviated.	
extra dimensions (Refs. [131–133])	neutrinos oscillate into sterile Kaluza–Klein modes that propagate in extra dimensions; in tension with reactor data.	
stochastic neutrino mixing (Ref. [134])	based on a difference between sterile neutrino mixing angles at production and detection (see also [135, 136]); fit worse than for vanilla ν_s .	
decoherence (Refs. [137, 138])	non-standard source of decoherence needed; known experimental energy resolutions constrain wave packet length, making an explanation by wave packet separation alone challenging.	
ν_s coupled to ultralight scalar (Ref. [139])	ultralight scalar coupling to ν_s and to ordinary matter affects sterile neutrino parameters; can not avoid reactor constraints	

Adding ingredients to the global analysis

LBL Acc + Solar + KamLAND

NO
IO

Large ("atmospheric")
mass splitting

$$\Delta m^2 = m_3^2 - \frac{1}{2}(m_1^2 + m_2^2)$$

- IO favored at 2σ level
- θ_{23} octant ambiguity
- CP conservation in NO ($\delta \approx n\pi$), inconsistent with it at $> 3\sigma$ in IO

Adding ingredients to the global analysis

NO
IO

- IO favored at 1.4σ level
- second θ_{23} octant is favored
- a strong indication for CP violation ($\sin \delta < 0$ at almost 4σ).

Adding ingredients to the global analysis

LBL Acc + Solar + KamLAND + short baseline reactors + SK+IC

NO
IO

- Different tendencies in global fit!
- Δm^2 precision 0.8%, sub-percentual for the first time
- Flipped preference for MO: **NO favored at 2.2σ level** (2.5σ in previous analysis)
- Flipped θ_{23} octant: **first octant favored at 1.1σ level**
- **CP conservation disfavored at 1.2σ level** (1.6σ in previous analysis)

Detector design

Largest liquid scintillator ever (20 kton) ,
equipped with 17612 large PMTs + 25600 small
PMTs to collect scintillation light

Experiment	Daya Bay	Borexino	KamLAND	JUNO
Target mass [t]	160	~300	~1000	~20000
Photo electrons / MeV	~160	~500	~250	~1600
Energy resolution @MeV	~8.5%	~5%	~6%	~3%
Photocathode coverage	12%	34%	34%	78%
Energy cal. Uncert.	0.5%	1.0%	2.0%	<1%

Calibrations in JUNO

JHEP 03 (2021) 004

Determination of e^+ non-linearity at $<1\%$ + optimization of energy resolution at $<3\%$ level

Radioactive sources (100-200 Hz) + Laser sources

Sources/Processes	Type	Radiation
^{137}Cs	γ	0.662 MeV
^{54}Mn	γ	0.835 MeV
^{60}Co	γ	1.173 + 1.333 MeV
^{40}K	γ	1.461 MeV
^{68}Ge	e^+	annihilation 0.511 + 0.511 MeV
$^{241}\text{Am-Be}$	n, γ	neutron + 4.43 MeV ($^{12}\text{C}^*$)
$^{241}\text{Am-}^{13}\text{C}$	n, γ	neutron + 6.13 MeV ($^{16}\text{O}^*$)
$(n, \gamma)\text{P}$	γ	2.22 MeV
$(n, \gamma)^{12}\text{C}$	γ	4.94 MeV or 3.68 + 1.26 MeV

Systematics budget

JUNO NMO sensitivity: 3σ (reactors only) in 6.5 y (with 26.6 GW_{th}) → 7.1 y with 11/12 reactor duty factor

- Combination **reactor + atmospheric** neutrino analysis **ongoing** → [further improve NMO sensitivity](#)
- Combination with **external Δm_{31}^2** long baseline experiments constraint → [enhanced NMO sensitivity](#)

Neutrino masses: tension with cosmology?

Cosmology provides tight constraints on the sum of neutrino masses Σ in Λ CDM model. Too tight?

DESI (April 2024) + CMB Planck + CMB Atacama Telescope:

- Best fit value: $\Sigma = 0$, and $\Sigma < 0.072$ eV at 95% CL
- Relaxing the $\Sigma > 0$ prior, negative neutrino masses are favored.

Long list of possible interpretations:

- Undetected systematics in DESI BAO data?
- Non-standard cosmology?
- New physics beyond the Λ CDM model?
- Exotic neutrino properties?

direct mass determinations crucial \Rightarrow KATRIN and beyond

Cosmology result on sum of masses

- It appears rather premature to quote a “consensus” upper bound on Σ from cosmological data at present.
- It could be better to quote a “range” of upper bounds, noticing that the 2σ cosmological limits on Σ cluster around a reasonable “geometric average” value of $\Sigma < 0.2$ eV, with variations up to a factor of 3 (upwards or downwards), depending on the specific model and dataset employed.
- It’s more conservative stating that $\Sigma < 0.2$ eV at 2σ (within a factor of 3) may be considered as a reasonable summary of acceptable and physically motivated current bounds, ranging from very conservative ($\Sigma < 0.60$ eV) to very aggressive ($\Sigma < 0.07$ eV).
- This interval of limits is essentially supported by Planck data alone within standard cosmology, as well as by both Planck and DESI in nonstandard cases.

Interaction channels

Liquid scintillator:
Linear alkylbenzenes

C – 88%
H – 12%

- $\bar{\nu}_e + p \rightarrow e^+ + n$
- $\nu + p \rightarrow \nu + p$
- $\nu + e \rightarrow \nu + e$
- $\nu_e + {}^{12}\text{C} \rightarrow e^- + {}^{12}\text{N}$
- $\bar{\nu}_e + {}^{12}\text{C} \rightarrow e^+ + {}^{12}\text{B}$

NC recoil threshold: 200 keV

JUNO site

Surface buildings / campus

- Surface Assembly Building
- LAB storage (5 kton)
- Water purification / Nitrogen
- Computing
- Power station
- Cable train
- Office / Dorm

~240 people working onsite now

Vertical Shaft, 563 m
put into use in 2023

Slope tunnel, 1265m

~ 650 m m.w.e.
 $R_{\mu} \sim 0.004 \text{ Hz/m}^2$
 $\langle E_{\mu} \rangle \sim 207 \text{ GeV}$

TAO: Taishan Antineutrino Observatory

Satellite detector located at 44 m from Taishan reactor

- 10 m² SiPM + 2.8 ton Gd-loaded LS @ -50 °C
- Energy resolution: $< 2\%/\sqrt{E}$, 4500 p.e./MeV

Main goal: measure the reactor neutrino spectrum (as a reference to JUNO) → sub-percent precision → reduce spectral shape systematics

Status:

Assembled at IHEP with ~100 SiPM
Disassembling, to be re-installed in the Taishan Nuclear Power Plant in 2024

arXiv:2005.08745

LPMs main specifications

Table 3

Summary of the 3-inch PMTs acceptance criteria and test results for different parameters. Results for class A parameters were from 2 value of vendor data after acceptance measurement introduced in Section 4.2, and other results were from acceptance measurement only all of the parameters were measured at 3×10^6 gain.

Parameters	Class	Requirement		Test fraction		Tolerance of diff.	Results (mean)
		(limit)	(mean)	HZC	JUNO		
Φ (glass bulb)	A	(78, 82) mm	–	100%	10%	–	OK
QE@420 nm	A	>22%	>24%	100%	10%	<5%	24.9%
High Voltage	A	(900,1300) V	–	100%	10%	<3%	1113 V
SPE resolution	A	<45%	<35%	100%	10%	<15%	33.2%
PV ratio	A	> 2	> 3	100%	10%	–	3.2
DCR@0.25 PE	A	<1.8 kHz	<1.0 kHz	100%	10%	–	512 Hz
DCR@3.0 PE	A	<30 Hz	–	100%	10%	–	7.2 Hz
TTS (σ)	B	<2.1 ns	–	–	3%	–	1.6 ns
Pre-pulse	B	<5%	<4.5%	–	3%	–	0.5%
After-pulse	B	<15%	<10%	–	3%	–	3.9%
QE non-uniformity	B	<11%	–	–	3%	–	5%
Φ (eff. cathode)	B	>74 mm	–	–	3%	–	77.2 mm
QE@320 nm	C	>5%	–	–	1%	–	10.2%
QE@550 nm	C	>5%	–	–	1%	–	8.6%
Aging	D	>200 nA years	–	–	3 PMTs	–	OK

Atmospheric neutrinos and MSW

$$P(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_\mu) \approx P(\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e) \approx \sin^2 \theta_{23} \sin^2 2\theta_{13}^m \sin^2 \left[1.27 \left(\Delta m_{31}^2 \right)^m \frac{L}{E_\nu} \right];$$

$$\sin^2 2\theta_{13}^m = \frac{\sin^2 2\theta_{13}}{\left(\cos 2\theta_{13} - A/\Delta m_{31}^2 \right)^2 + \sin^2 2\theta_{13}}$$

Downward events: they don't cross relevantly the Earth, so $A \sim 0$, therefore the oscillation probability in vacuum holds and there are no differences between NO and IO.

Upward events: MSW resonance takes place according to the sign of the ratio $A/\Delta m_{31}^2$.

For ν , $A > 0$ holds: MSW takes place if $\Delta m_{31}^2 > 0$, that is NO

For anti- ν , $A < 0$ holds: MSW takes place if $\Delta m_{31}^2 < 0$, that is IO

$$P_{\text{NH}}(\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta) = P_{\text{IH}}(\bar{\nu}_\alpha \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\beta), P_{\text{IH}}(\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta) = P_{\text{NH}}(\bar{\nu}_\alpha \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_\beta)$$

Calibration strategy

Calibration of non-linearity

- 1) physics non-linearity → radioactive sources + cosmogenic isotope ^{12}B
- 2) instrum. non-linearity → laser source

Systematics understanding and control

- rad. sources syst (shadowing, non uniformity)
- PMTs syst. (dark noise, non linearity, ...)

Optimization and calibration of energy resolution

- position non-uniformity: source in multiple positions

Non-linearity

Systematics

Resolution

Hardware & sources

- 1D: Automatic Calibration Unit (ACU)
- 2D: Cable Loop System (CLS)
- 3D: Remotely Operated under-LS Vehicles (ROV)

Calibrations: non uniformity correction

Non-uniformity is corrected by calibrating multiple positions with radioactive (AmC) sources

$g(R,\theta)$: radial-angular non-uniformity correction

* marks calibration points

Mapping the detector with AmC source

Calibration program

Program structured following three time periods

1) Comprehensive calibrations

- basic understanding of the CD performance
- At the beginning of data-taking
- > 250 points, ~48h

Source	Energy [MeV]	Points
Neutron (Am-C)	2.22	250
Neutron (Am-Be)	4.4	1
Laser	/	10
^{68}Ge	0.511×2	1
^{137}Cs	0.662	1
^{54}Mn	0.835	1
^{60}Co	1.17+1.33	1
^{40}K	1.461	1
Total	/	/

2) Monthly calibrations

- Monitor non-uniformity
- ~100 points, ~11h

System	Source	Points
ACU	Neutron (Am-C)	27
ACU	Laser	27
CLS	Neutron (Am-C)	40
GT	Neutron (Am-C)	23
Total	/	/

3) Weekly calibrations

- track major changes of the detector → variations in the light yield of the LS, PMT gains, and electronics
- central axis, 0.1% precision on gamma peaks

Source	Energy [MeV]	Points
Neutron (Am-C)	2.22	5
Laser	/	10
Total	/	/

Non-linearity optimization

- **Physics nonlinearity** = non-linearity between particle energy and scintillating/Cherenkov photon
 - LS property, position independent
 - γ calibration sources
 - + ^{12}B cosmogenic isotope
- **Instrumental nonlinearity** = nonlinearity between photon and charge for each channel.
 - PMT instrumentation property
 - Position dependent
 - Laser calib. source→ dual calorimetry technique → compare LPMTs and sPMTS response

Goal: determination of e+ non-linearity at <1% level

Neutrinos from natural sources

Solar ν
0.1-10 MeV

Geo ν
few MeV

Supernova ν
tens of MeV

Atmospheric ν
~0.5-100 GeV

Energy

Expected rates

${}^7\text{Be}$: ~10000/day
CNO: ~1000/day
 ${}^8\text{B}$: ~90/day

~400 / year

- Core Collapse SN
@ 10 kpc: ~ 10^3 in sec.
- Diffuse SN: few / year

Several / day

New physics?

- Proton decay
- Neutrino magnetic moment
- Sterile neutrinos
- Non Standard Interactions
- Lorentz invariance
- Others

Shape uncertainties of the JUNO detector

Shape uncertainties of the JUNO detector, presented relative to the number of IBD events from Taishan and Yangjiang reactors in each bin. The absolute uncertainties are obtained by generating simulated samples where systematic parameters are varied based on their assumed uncertainties and taking square roots of diagonal elements of the resulting covariance matrices.

The NMO discriminator contour for JUNO exposure and energy resolution at 1 MeV for NO Asimov data set.

The resolution is scanned by varying a and fixing $b = 0.64 \times 10^{-2}$, $c = 1.20 \times 10^{-2}$ MeV.

The gray, black, and green contour lines stand for 3σ , 4σ , and 5σ significance. The top pad shows the time evolution of the $|\Delta\chi^2_{\min}|$ under the 2.8%, 2.9%, and 3.0% energy resolution at 1 MeV. The right pad shows the required energy resolution to achieve different $|\Delta\chi^2_{\min}|$ under the JUNO exposure of ~ 6 years \times 26.6 GW_{th} (data taking time of 6.7 years).

Systematic effect	Count	Relative uncertainty, %	
		input	rate
JUNO systematic uncertainty	{13+340}		1.5
$\sin^2 \theta_{13}$	1	3.2	0.14
Matter density (MSW)	1	6.1	0.066
Detector normalization	1	1.0	1.1
Energy resolution	3	0.19, 0.47, 0.83	1.6×10^{-7}
Background rates	{7}		1.0
Accidentals	1	1.0	0.020
${}^9\text{Li}/{}^8\text{He}$	1	20	0.40
Fast neutrons	1	100	0.25
${}^{13}\text{C}(\alpha, n){}^{16}\text{O}$	1	50	0.062
Geoneutrinos	1	30	0.89
Atmospheric neutrinos	1	50	0.20
World reactors	1	2.0	0.050
Background shape	340		0.019
${}^9\text{Li}/{}^8\text{He}$	(340)	10	0.0072
Fast neutrons	(340)	20	0.0016
${}^{13}\text{C}(\alpha, n){}^{16}\text{O}$	(340)	50	0.0032
Geoneutrinos	(340)	5.0	0.015
Atmospheric neutrinos	(340)	50	0.0063
World reactors	(340)	5.0	0.0060
IBD spectrum shape uncertainty from TAO [†]	340	0.73 – 14	0.12

Summary of the systematic effects which impact the JUNO detector.

Boosting NMO sensitivity w/ atmospheric

ν /anti- ν asymmetry in MSW resonance thanks to matter effects (4-30 GeV):

oscillation probabilities for NO and IO are different due to ν path through the Earth matter.

Upgoing muon ν : MSW resonance takes place according to $\text{sign}(A/\Delta m_{3\ell}^2)$, where $A = \nu$ -matter potential

$$P(\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e) \approx 1 - \sin^2 2\theta_{13}^m \sin^2 \left[1.27 \left(\Delta m_{31}^2 \right)^m \frac{L}{E_\nu} \right];$$

$$\sin^2 2\theta_{13}^m = \frac{\sin^2 2\theta_{13}}{\left(\cos 2\theta_{13} - A/\Delta m_{31}^2 \right)^2 + \sin^2 2\theta_{13}}$$

ν : $A > 0 \rightarrow$ MSW if $\Delta m_{3\ell}^2 > 0 \rightarrow$ NO
 anti- ν : $A < 0 \rightarrow$ MSW if $\Delta m_{3\ell}^2 < 0 \rightarrow$ IO

$$L \approx -D_{Earth} \cos(\theta), \quad \theta > 90^\circ$$

$$L \approx 0, \quad \text{otherwise}$$

Combination reactor + atmospheric neutrino analysis ongoing

Oscillation patterns for atmospheric exp.

Normal Ordering (NO)

Inverted Ordering (IO)

